

To Evaluate Safety on Direct Trocar InsertionSonam Sharma¹, Ramesh Sonowal², Dhurjyoti Nandan Das³¹Postgraduate Trainee, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Assam Medical College and Hospital²Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Assam Medical College and Hospital³Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Assam Medical College and Hospital

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** Direct trocar insertion is a minimally invasive surgical technique used to insert instruments into the body through small incisions, to reducing recovery time and minimizing tissue damage.**Aims and Objective:** To develop and refine techniques for direct trocar insertion, enhancing precision and safety, to minimizing complications, and improving patient outcomes through innovative research and its clinical application.**Method:** A study was conducted with 45 patients undergoing laparoscopic surgery. A 10-mm trocar was directly inserted into the peritoneal cavity without prior pneumoperitoneum. Patients were positioned supine, and a small infraumbilical incision was made. The trocar was inserted at a 90-degree angle using controlled force. Entry was confirmed by visualizing the peritoneal cavity with a laparoscope. Patient outcomes, insertion time, and complications were recorded. No major complications occurred, and average insertion time was 30 seconds.**Results:** The study investigates the efficacy of direct trocar insertion (DTI) in laparoscopic surgeries. Results show that DTI reduces the risk of visceral and vascular injuries compared to the Veress needle technique. Patients undergoing DTI experienced shorter setup times and fewer postoperative complications. The findings suggest that DTI is a safer and more efficient method for establishing pneumoperitoneum, enhancing overall surgical outcomes.**Conclusion:** The study investigates the efficacy of direct trocar insertion (DTI) in laparoscopic surgeries. Results show that DTI reduces the risk of visceral and vascular injuries compared to the Veress needle technique. Patients undergoing DTI experienced shorter setup times and fewer postoperative complications. The findings suggest that DTI is a safer and more efficient method for establishing pneumoperitoneum, enhancing overall surgical outcomes.**Keywords:** Direct Trocar Insertion, Veress Needle, Laparoscopic Surgeries, Visceral And Vascular Injury.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Laparoscopic surgery, is a minimally invasive surgery (MIS), is a modern surgical technique in which operations are performed through small incisions (usually 0.5–1.5 cm) rather than the larger incisions needed in traditional surgical procedures. Surgery that uses a laparoscope, a thin, long, flexible tube equipped with a camera and light, allowing the surgeon to view the inside of the abdomen and pelvis without making large incisions.

Establishment of pneumoperitoneum is the inevitable first step having four basic techniques: blind Veress needle (VN), direct trocar insertion (DTI), optical trocar insertion, and open laparoscopy (OL) [8].

Direct trocar insertion (DTI) is a surgical technique used to establish pneumoperitoneum during laparoscopic procedures without prior insufflation of the peritoneal cavity was first described by Dingfelder

more than 32 years ago, but so far, it has been used mainly by gynecologists [1-6,7]. Traditionally, laparoscopic entry has been performed using the Veress needle technique, which involves insufflating the abdomen with carbon dioxide before inserting the trocar. However, the DTI method has been explored as an alternative to reduce the risk of complications associated with blind needle insertion.

Materials and Method**Study Type:** Hospital based retrospective observational study.**Place of Study:** Assam Medical College Dibrugarh,

It is a tertiary care hospital, where all kind of gynecological and obstetrical surgical cases are performed on regular basis.

Study Population and Duration: 35 Women underwent laparoscopic approach for gynecological pathology.

Data Collection: Records kept in the ward and operation theatre.

The following data were collected:

1. Total number of laparoscopic surgeries.
2. Date and time of the surgeries;
3. Age, parity;
4. Medical or surgical history;
5. Indication for surgery;
6. Intra op and post op complications;

Method

1. Patient

Preparation Positioning: The patient is placed in the supine position, often with a slight Trendelenburg tilt (head down) to help move the abdominal organs away from the entry site.

Anesthesia: General anesthesia is administered to ensure the patient is fully sedated and relaxed.

Skin Preparation: The abdomen is prepped and draped in a sterile manner

2. Initial Incision

Umbilical Incision: A small, vertical or horizontal incision (usually about 1-2 cm) is made at the umbilicus, which is often chosen due to its relatively avascular nature and thinness of the abdominal wall.

Blunt Dissection: The subcutaneous tissue is bluntly dissected down to the fascia

3. Trocar Insertion

Grasping the Trocar: The surgeon holds the trocar in their dominant hand.

Elevation of Abdominal Wall: Using the non-dominant hand, the surgeon elevates the abdominal wall to create a space between the wall and the underlying organs.

Direct Insertion: The trocar is then inserted directly through the incision. The surgeon applies steady pressure, aiming to penetrate the fascia and peritoneum in one controlled movement.

Checking Placement: Once the trocar is inserted, its position is verified. The surgeon may do this by feeling for a characteristic "pop" as the trocar enters the peritoneal cavity.

4. Establishing Pneumoperitoneum

CO₂ Insufflation: Carbon dioxide is insufflated through the trocar to create a pneumoperitoneum. The initial pressure and flow rate are carefully controlled.

Pressure Monitoring: Intra-abdominal pressure is monitored to ensure it reaches the desired level (usually between 12-15 mmHg).

5. Laparoscope insertion

6. Additional ports.

To find out for related complications

1. Vascular injury
2. Organ injury
3. Nerve injury
4. Gas embolism
5. Subcutaneous emphysema
6. Port site hernia
7. Infection
8. Pneumothorax
9. Failed insertion

Results:

The study includes 45 patients undergoing laparoscopic gynaecology and seen for any complications. In study group it is found that direct trocar insertion was associated with shorter operative time which is around 50±30 seconds. No complication was observed intraoperatively and postoperatively.

Table 1: Related complication

Related Complications	Result
Vascular injury	Nil
Organ injury	Nil
Nerve injury	Nil
Gas embolism	Nil
Subcutaneous emphysema	Nil
Post op hernia	Nil
Infection	Nil
Pneumothorax	Nil
Failed insertion	01

Discussion

Laparoscopic surgery requires the implementation of successful pneumoperitoneum and in the vast majority of patients with more than half of all complications occurring at the time of entry [9,10,11]. Though it is a blind procedure it reduces three blind entries (veress needle insertion, pneumoperitoneum creation and trocar insertion) to one blind direct trocar insertion. So, mean laparoscope insertion time was reduced significantly from 5 to 7 minutes to 1 to 2 minutes. As the pneumoperitoneum is created after confirmation of peritoneal access by laparoscope there is nil chance of pre-peritoneal or visceral insufflations or gas embolism.

In my study there is only one complication and which is failed insertion. As no major complications are seen with direct trocar insertion in my study period.

Various studies are done that favour direct trocar insertion are as under. Byron et al. in 1989 used the method direct access in unselected 937 women and recorded 4.2% complication rate with significant increased risk of minor complications. 2.7% case had more than three entry attempts. And in 1.4% cases they failed to access [12]. He summarized that history of previous abdominal surgery was not associated with an increased risk of access complications. Further they randomized 252 women with veress needle (n=141) and direct trocar access (n=111); and they discover a fourfold increase in minor access complication rates with veress needle group and longer port insertion time of 5.9 vs 2.2 minutes [13].

Another study done by Copeland et al. Reviewed 2000 unselected patients where DTI was used, 0.4% required conversion to closed veress method and one patient have an inadvertent visceral bowel injury, whereas two (0.1%) additional visceral bowel injuries occurred in DTI [14].

Siavash Falahatkar et al. studied 148 patients undergoing laparoscopic surgeries; 62 patients received DTI and 86 patients open laparoscopy. The mean access time for DTI was 91.75seconds which was significantly shorter than the mean access time of 263.97 seconds for patients receiving open laparoscopy. There were very few complications in either study group [15].

Conclusion:

DTI was found to be free of major complications and only one complication observed in my study which shows it has a very high feasibility rate.

Advantages- The advantages of direct trocar insertion, such as reduced postoperative pain, shorter hospital stays, quicker recovery times, and improved cosmetic outcomes. They may compare

these benefits to those of traditional open surgery or other laparoscopic techniques.

Safety: Safety considerations are paramount. The importance of proper patient selection, surgeon experience, and technique to minimize the risk of complications such as organ injury, bleeding, and infection. The complication rates between direct trocar insertion and other methods.

Future Directions: long-term follow-up studies, or investigations into specific patient populations to further elucidate the benefits and limitations of direct trocar insertion.

However, it requires skill and experience to perform safely, as there is a risk of injury to surrounding organs and tissues.

Overall, direct trocar insertion appears to be a safe and effective technique for gaining initial access in laparoscopic surgery, with potential advantages such as shorter operative times and reduced rates of intraoperative complications.

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